

Subjective Criteria for blind Observers

MRI

DDFT Tendinopathy parasagittal/sagittal splits

mild = narrow linear areas of increased SI on T1 sequences at the suprasesamoidean portion, or at sesamoidean portion, or at the infrasesamoidean portion of the DDF tendon.

moderate = narrow linear areas of increased SI on T1GE and PD and intermediate SI T2 and STIR FSE sequences at the suprasesamoidean and sesamoidean portions, or at the sesamoidean and infrasesamoidean portions of the DDF tendon.

severe = wide linear areas of increased SI on T1GE and PD and intermediate SI T2 and STIR FSE sequences or thin increased SI T2 and STIR sequences at the suprasesamoidean, sesamoidean and infrasesamoidean portions of the DDF tendon.

DDFT Tendinopathy dorsal borders

mild = diffuse irregularity of the dorsal margin of the DDF tendon visible on T1GE, PD, T2 and STIR FSE sequences.

moderate = multifocal irregularity of the dorsal margin of the DDF tendon visible on T1GE, PD, T2 and STIR FSE sequences.

severe = prominent irregularity with defects in the dorsal margin of the DDF tendon visible on T1GE, PD, T2 and STIR FSE sequences.

NB Defects

mild = flattening, shallow concavity and/or decreased density in the compact bone of the sagittal ridge of the NB extending medially or laterally. Erosions had increased SI on all sequences.

moderate = focal defect or area of increased SI on all sequences at the sagittal ridge of the NB and/or decreased density in the compact and trabecular bone of the NB flexor surface.

severe = extensive defect or area of increased SI on all sequences on the sagittal ridge of the NB and/or decreased density in the compact and trabecular bone of the NB flexor surface.

Bursa effusion

mild = synovial fluid in the proximal recess of the bursa with mild dorsal displacement of the synovial membrane. No synovial membrane proliferation or thickening.

moderate = synovial fluid in proximal recess of the bursa with moderate dorsal displacement of the collateral sesamoidean ligament. No synovial membrane proliferation or thickening.

severe = full distension of the proximal recess of the bursa and marked dorsal displacement of the collateral sesamoidean ligament. No synovial membrane proliferation or thickening

Adhesions/synovial masses

mild

moderate

severe

Bursography

Fibrocartilage lesions

mild = contrast line ill-defined or disrupted only lateral OR medial

moderate = likewise as in M, however the disruption is visible lateral AND medial, but in < 50% the whole length of the flexor surface

severe = likewise as in Mo, but the disruption is visible > 50% the whole length of flexor surface

DDFT Tendinopathy dorsal borders

mild = palmar surface of the proximal recess of the bursa in 1/3 irregular

moderate = Likewise M, irregularity in > 1/3 but < 2/3 the palmar surface

severe = likewise Mo, irregularity > 2/3

DDFT Tendinopathy sagittal/parasagittal

mild = escape of the contrast-agent from the palmar surface of the bursa (LM projection) into tendon or palmar escape of the contrast-agent (skyline projection). The contrast agent is not through the tendon and the leakage is visible only in one lobe / or axial.

moderate = likewise M but the leakage escape of the contrast agent involves both lobes of the DDFT

severe = likewise with M OR Mo, but the escape / leakage of the contrast agent involves the whole length of the tendon in the proximal recess (LM projection) or the leakage is through the tendon (skyline projection)

Bursa effusion

mild = shape of the bursa not like comma and proximal recess limit < the proximal limit of P2

moderate = likewise the M but proximal recess limit = the proximal limit of P2

severe = likewise M but proximal recess limit > the proximal limits of P2

Ultrasound

DDFT Tendinopathy/Adhesions/Synovial masses

mild = only one lobe is affected

moderate = both lobes are affected, but in <50% the bursa surface

severe = the lesions are extended > 50% of the bursa surface

Bursitis / Effusion

mild = proximal border of the bursa does not overcome the proximal border of the palmar recess of the DIP.

moderate = proximal border of the bursa in the same level as the proximal border of the palmar recess of the DIP

severe = proximal border of the bursa overcomes the proximal border of the palmar recess of the DIP